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Influence Of Culture On People’s Environmental Literacy

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of culture on environmental literacy. Specifically, it investigates the influence of culture on people’s environmental knowledge, attitude and practices. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design using a total of two hundred and fifty (250) people of different cultural backgrounds purposively selected from five local government areas enumerated in Ibadan metropolis. Three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.01 level of significance. The instruments used for data collection were Cultural Practices Questionnaire (0.78), Environmental Knowledge Test (0.75), Environmental Attitude Questionnaire (0.77) and Environmental Practices Questionnaire (0.78). Data were analysed using tables, Kendall’s tau and Spearman’s rho statistical analyses. The results show that culture has significant influence on people’s environmental knowledge, attitude and practices in Ibadan metropolis. Thus, different cultural leaders should encourage pro-environmental cultural practices among their followers. Governments should consider and acknowledge people’s culture and also, encourage the participation of local communities when formulating environmental intervention policies and programmes.

Keywords: Culture, Environmental knowledge, Attitude and Practices, Environmental literacy

INTRODUCTION

The environment encompasses the physical, biological, social and cultural systems that surround and interact with humans, influencing their well-being, behaviour and relationships (Kenneth, 2020). It includes the natural and built environments, as well as the social, economic, and cultural actors that impact human health and well-being (World Health Organisation, 2020). It is a social construct, shaped by human perceptions, values, and practices which influence their relationships with nature (King, 2020). As noted by Wallace (2018), the environment is not only the sum of all the material things that constantly interact with one another; it also includes the economic structures, the outlook and habit of peoples in different parts of the globe. The environment as a whole, therefore, includes all things (living and non-living), influences and conditions in human’s vicinity which may be natural, socio-economic or cultural having impact on an human’s life and development.

Today, the global environment is experiencing various ecological challenges as it had never encountered before as a result of the growing and continuous human activities on the planet earth. Such challenges

include among others, ozone layer depletion, global warming, climate change, pollution, environment-related health problems, flooding as well as erosion (Fashona, 2019). Environmental problems occur in all countries and at every developmental phase, but they differ in nature, enormity and intricacy. The implications of human's brutality on the environment are serious throughout the world and specifically in the developing countries. Nigeria, like many other developing countries of the world do experience series of environmental problems such as drought, desertification, flooding, pollution, erosion, deforestation, municipal waste management problem, open defecation, to mention few. In the year 2024 report by the World Statistics, Nigeria ranked ninth and recorded 18.7 per cent.

Environments of most urban cities in Nigeria are increasingly degraded and are ranked among urban cities with the lowest liveability index in the world (Global Liveability Index 2024). Nigeria recorded 37.5% and ranked 141 out of the 180 countries surveyed for the 2024 environmental performance index. Despite the environmental efforts at eradicating environmental problems in Nigeria, the situational reports show that significant improvement has not been achieved. Responsible environmental behaviour has not fully become the way of life (culture) in third world countries particularly in Nigeria (Olajojo, 2016). The saying "mi o le fi owo ra eko, ki n tun fi owo da ewe re nu", meaning "I cannot buy pap with money and still use money to dispose its wrapper" strongly shows the level of people's attitude towards sanitation. No wonder the Nigerian environment continues to depreciate in quality.

Ibadan which is the capital city of Oyo State in Nigeria is bedeviled with environmental problems especially, in the metropolitan city. There is direct dumping of solid wastes (domestic, agricultural and industrial) in open dumps, rivers, buildings under construction and even open defecation by both young and adult. This practice is seen as one of the major serious challenges confronting the city (Fawole, 2024; Adelekan, 2016). Environment-related health challenges, such as typhoid, dysentery, cholera and diarrhea, are prevalent especially among the urban poor (Adelekan, 2016). This perhaps informs the submission of Gbadamosi (2015) who points out that of all costs of environmental deterioration, especially in urban areas, havoc to people's health is by far the uppermost.

The acquisition of environmental knowledge, attitudes and practices that provide lasting solutions to environmental problems make one to be environmentally literate. Hence, environmental literacy is described according to Orr (1992) as the capability for a contextual and detailed understanding on an environmental problem in order to enable for analysis, synthesis, evaluation, and ultimately sound and informed decision making at a citizen's level. Environmental literacy is about knowledge, feelings, practices and activities grounded in familiarity and sound knowledge toward improving the quality of the environment (Schneider, 1997). Environmental literacy seeks to modify the behaviour of human so that human can relate with the environment in a friendly and sustainable manner. The future of our country strongly relies on a cultured public who will become stewards of the very environment that keeps us going, our households, communities and incoming generations.

Understanding the root causes and effects of environmental damage as well as the costs and benefits of an action is essential. Macionis (2017) noticed that none of the environmental problems confronting human beings now is a product of 'natural world' operating on its own. Each of the problems results from the specific actions of human beings and are, therefore, social issues which have their origins as well as their panacea in the society. By implication, these actions are embedded in people's culture which is a design of living in a particular society. Since there are different societies with different cultures, there are different cultural practices (actions) having effects on the environment. Cultural practices are generally norms in behaviours and standards that developed in ethnic groups and communities in ancient history. They include broad range of activities, such as religious practices, interpersonal relationships, child care, and knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe.

Corroborating the foregoing, Onyeabochukwu (2020), affirmed that the cultural practices of people do not only affect their health, but also affect all their affairs with the environment where they live. For example, it is a taboo in some Nigerian societies to pour hot water on the ground, this is in connection with the belief that the ground or soil is a spirit being which must not be hurt. The Yorubas for instance, do not just dig the ground for any purpose without due permission from the soil. Also, the Ibos do celebrate new

yam festival purposely to appreciate the “mother” earth (soil) for opening her bowels to bring out the produce. In similar vein, motorists are so cautious not to kill animals (insects inclusive) while on motion. More so, the indigenous people do not hit, beat nor cut trees, bushes and grasses anyhow without taking necessary steps (Ogunade, 2007).

Despite the foregoing cultural mindset, some scholars have revealed some of the havocs which some traditional cultural practices pose to the environment. For instance, Bisong (2018); Pelemo (2015); and Milton (2012) pointed the high consumption of wild resources (bush meat), unregulated bush burning during hunting expeditions and farming preparations, disregarding the rules of environmental hygiene in the name of tradition, and many others, as traditional cultural practices which have done more harm and posed serious threat to natural environmental structures.

Therefore, understanding the role of culture is key to tackling environmental challenges. Thus, the environmental problems in Nigeria and Ibadan to be precise, cannot be divulged from people’s culture. On the strength of this observation, this research investigated the influence of culture on people’s environmental literacy.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was to investigate the influence of culture on environmental literacy.

Specifically, the study was out to:

- (a) determine the relationship between people’s culture and their environmental knowledge.
- (b) examine the extent to which people’s culture affect their attitude to the environment.
- (c) find out the influence culture has on people’s environmental practices.

Hypotheses

In the course of this research work, the following research hypotheses were tested:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between people’s culture and their environmental knowledge.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between people’s culture and their attitude to environment.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between people’s culture and their environmental practices.

Theoretical Framework

Vygotsky’s Sociocultural Theory

Sociocultural approaches to learning and development were first systematized and applied by Vygotsky and his collaborators in Russia in the year 1978. To them, human actions occur in their specific cultural contexts, with this, human behaviour is easier and better understood vis-à-vis his cultural background. The spread of Vygotsky’s thoughts and the usage of his work in different national backgrounds have contributed to “a multifaceted related but heterogeneous proposals”.

Sociocultural theory is an up-and-coming theory in psychology that examines the vital roles which the society contributes to human development. It lays emphasis on the importance of interaction between the people and the culture in which they live. The theory states that people learn from social interaction within a cultural context. It is of the view that people are products of their social and cultural environment, and stresses how social and cultural influences have effect on people’s thinking and learning. Knowledge is thus a product of humans and is socially and culturally constructed (Rogoff; Radziszewska, and Masiello, 1995).

Sociocultural theory clarifies how individual mental functioning is connected to cultural, institutional, and historical context.

Vygotsky’s sociocultural theory is relevant to this study as it acknowledges the great influences in which the surrounding, social and cultural factors have on people’s behaviour. The theory highly recognizes the roles which the variable of the study – culture plays in people’s environmental literacy. This theory confirms the view of this study which points out that people are the products of their social and cultural environments and lays emphasis on how social and cultural influences affect the cognitive and psychological world of people.

Empirical Literature Review

Culture and People's Environmental Knowledge, Attitude and Practices

Arbuthnot and Lingg (1985) compared the environmental knowledge, attitude and behaviour of the French and Americans cultures. They found the Americans' knowledge about the environment to be more than that of the French. Thus, American's attitudes were discovered to be more pro-ecological than their French counterparts. These findings are attributed to the fact that Americans engage in habitual environmentally-friendly actions while the French are found to be more preoccupied with their personal economic gain or loss when faced with environmental questions. Hence, they involve in activities which are anti-ecological than the Americans. A cross sectional survey was carried out by Oyemade, Omokhodion, Olawuyi, and Sridhar (2009) to determine the relationship between culturally hygiene practices and environmental knowledge of Ibadan women. Amidst other findings, the educational background coupled with sanitary activities carried out by a group of women helped them to have better environmental knowledge than the other group.

Ebong (2021) in one of his studies assessed the environmental health knowledge and practice of 192 students at Ja'afaru secondary school in Zaria, Nigeria by means of questionnaire. The findings indicated that students with literate parents, adequate opportunities and sanitation facilities at home had higher environmental knowledge than the students with illiterate parents, inadequate opportunities and sanitation facilities at home. The latter students' knowledge of environmental hygiene was low because of lack of sanitation facilities and opportunities to practice sanitary activities at home.

Variables which predict environmental concern of people to "green buying" (buying products that are environmentally beneficial) were investigated by Maineri, Barnett and Valdero (2011) among 201 respondents in 8 middle-class communities in Los Angeles. The predictor variables included specific cultural beliefs of consumers, awareness about environmental impacts of products, economic status and demographic variables of consumers. The results of hierarchical multiple regression analyses supported the hypotheses under study: specific cultural beliefs predicted several green-buying behaviours and attitudes, followed by economic status, awareness about the environmental impacts of products, and demographic variables of consumers respectively.

A study conducted by Oladepo and Sridhar (2012) among large ethnic groups in Nigeria found that many of the people's traditional practices promoted good environmental and complemented modern environmental promotion efforts. According to them, folklores and songs emphasize sanitary disposal of human waste, general cleanliness and the importance of personal hygiene. Odewole (2022) and Chukwu (2020) in their different studies on the relevance of culture on students' environmental attitude found that there was positive significant relationship between students' cultures and their attitude to environment.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive research design of survey type. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting people of different cultural backgrounds while simple random sampling was used in selecting the participants for the study. A total of two hundred and fifty (250) participants were selected across the five local government areas enumerated in Ibadan metropolis. The instruments used for data collection were Cultural Practices Questionnaire (0.78), Environmental Knowledge Test (0.75), Environmental Attitude (0.77) and Environmental Practices (0.78) Questionnaires. The instrument were validated accordingly: Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient of both Environmental Attitude and Practices Questionnaires. The coded scores in Environment Knowledge Test were subjected to Kuder Richardson 20. Data collected were analysed using Kendall's tau and Spearman's rho statistical tools.

RESULTS

Data collected for the study were subjected to analysis based on the three hypotheses formulated for the study. The results are presented as thus:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between people’s culture and their environmental knowledge.

Table 1: Correlations between Culture and Environmental Knowledge

			Culture	Environmental knowledge
Kendall's tau_b	Culture	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.822**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	26	26
	Environmental knowledge	Correlation Coefficient	.822**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	26	26
Spearman's rho	Culture	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.941**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	26	26
	Environmental knowledge	Correlation Coefficient	.941**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	26	26

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 shows the correlation between respondents’ culture and their environmental knowledge which is shown to be 0.822 using Kendall’s tau and a value of 0.941 using Spearman’s rho which are all significant at (P = 0.01). This implies that there is significant positive correlation between the two variables, that is, culture and environmental knowledge. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between people’s culture and their attitude to environment.

Table 2: Correlations between Culture and Environmental Attitude

			Culture	Environmental attitude
Kendall's tau_b	Culture	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.786**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	26	26
	Environmental attitude	Correlation Coefficient	.786**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	26	26
Spearman's rho	Culture	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.897**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	26	26
	Environmental attitude	Correlation Coefficient	.897**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	26	26

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 reveals the correlation between culture and environmental attitude. The values of 0.786 and 0.897 using Kendall's tau and Spearman's rho respectively were gotten. Hence, the correlation is significant at 0.01 level. The values indicate that there is significant positive correlation between culture and environmental attitude. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not accepted.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between people's culture and their environmental practices.

Table 3: Correlations between Culture and Environmental Practices

			Culture	Environmental practices
Kendall's tau_b	Culture	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.902**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	26	26
	Environmental practices	Correlation Coefficient	.902**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	26	26
Spearman's rho	Culture	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.966**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	26	26
	Environmental practices	Correlation Coefficient	.966**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	26	26

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From table 3, the correlation between respondents' culture and environmental practices are shown to be 0.902 using Kendall's tau and 0.966 using Spearman's rho which are all significant at 0.01 level. This means that there is significant positive correlation between culture and environmental practices. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of this study showed that there was strong and positive significant, relationship between people's culture and their environmental knowledge. This result might be confirming the fact that culture provides explanation on the existence and relevance of natural phenomena especially to human beings, and as a result of this, spells out the type of relationship that should take place between human being and environment. Culture is rich in providing environmental information. The involvement of people in various cultural practices especially, the environment-related activities exposes them to certain ideas and facts which make them to know more about the natural environment. For instance, a traditional herbal doctor who prepares herbal mixture tends to have a fair knowledge about vegetation – plants, flowers, shrubs and trees including their relevance to human health and survival. Moreover, all cultures cherish cleanliness - body and home hygiene are taken to be germane. As people engage in different household cleaning activities - sweeping of rooms in the home and its environment, clearing of gutters, cutting of bushes/grasses, washing of plates and other kitchen utensils, among others, they know more about what cleanliness entails and its relevance to environmental health and safety. Therefore, individuals who actively engage in different cultural activities especially those ones related to environment tend to perform better in achievement test on environmental concepts. This finding corroborates Oyemade, Omokhodion, Olawuyi and Sridhar (2009); Ebong (2014) and that of Onyeabochukwu (2020) whose

studies revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between people's cultural practices and their environmental knowledge. This study also observes that there was significant relationship, though low between people's culture and their attitude to the environment. The significant relationship could be attributed to the fact that people's culture largely determine their disposition towards the environment. There are many cultural activities which are environment-friendly. The more people engage in a number of such activities (tree replanting, sanitary activities, conservation efforts, etc), the more and better they develop favourable feelings towards the environment. The best way of developing responsible and desirable environmental attitude in the people is by actively involving them in those activities which can help in enhancing their feelings. This is so because attitude is not like any other concepts which can be taught and taken "hook-line-and-sinker", but are better developed when people are exposed to certain activities capable of building and developing favourable feelings which later lead to the formation of desirable attitude. It could be deduced from the foregoing the people's cultural beliefs and practices tend to influence their feelings and concern about the environment.

However, Adelekan (2016) reports that people's cultural practices relatively contribute to their environmental attitude. This means that the display of negative cultural practices by people might hinder their feelings and dispositions to environment because attitudes are formed as a result of certain learning experiences. This might explain the reason why the relationship between people's culture and environmental attitude is low in this study. This result is in line with that of Odewole (2022), Chukwu (2020), Maineri, Barnett and Valdero (2011), among others.

Still on the outcomes of the study, there is positive significant relationship between people's culture and environmental practices. This finding shows that people's cultural practices are related with their environmental practices. This result might emanate from the fact that culture is the basis of all human actions. People's cultural practices influence their behaviour and actions toward the environment. Cultural practices determine the kind and level of relationship that should exist between the people and the environment. In some areas, the local culture and laws emphasize environmental protection while in others, this has not been a major concern. For instance, both Osun sacred grove and river are taken to be sacred natural elements forbidden for illegal lumbering and disposal of wastes respectively. Osun grove and river, and many other cultural tourist areas are well taken care of in terms of beautification which improves the aesthetic values of the environment. Moreso, culture in terms of folklores, songs and wise sayings emphasize sanitary disposal of human waste, general cleanliness and the importance of personal hygiene. A study conducted by Oladepo and Sridhar (2015) among large ethnic groups in Nigeria found that many of the people's traditional practices promoted good environmental practices and complemented modern environmental promotion efforts. This result is in tandem with the reports of Onyeabochukwu (2020), Oladepo and Sridhar (2015), and Ogunade (2007).

CONCLUSION

Results from this study reveal that there is significant relationship between people's culture and environmental literacy. Specifically, people's cultural practices influence their environmental knowledge, attitude to environment and environmental practices especially, in Ibadan metropolis. Though, the significance level is low for attitude to environment. From the study, it is evident that culture remains critical in any environmental discourse especially, environmental literacy. The study exposes the relevance of culture (people's cultural backgrounds) and cultural leaders in curbing environmental problems especially, the humanly induced ones as people need a change of attitude and behaviour in order to solve the problem of persistent poor environmental attitude and practices among the people in Ibadan metropolis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Having determined the relationship between people's cultural backgrounds and their environmental knowledge, cultural leaders should further encourage pro-environmental cultural beliefs and practices among their adherents. Cultural leaders remain critical stakeholders in influencing and shaping

environment-related attitude and behaviour. The Nigerian government should consider the integration of cultural leaders in the planning, decision-making and implementation of environmental policies and projects at the local, state and federal levels. When solving environment-related problems, people's cultural backgrounds should be highly considered in order to get a lasting solution to such problem(s). The present day traditional environmentalists should embark on day-to-day sensitization programme which would showcase the relevance of indigenous environment-related culture to environmental literacy.

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